

Developing Social Apps and Websites as a Tool of L2 Learning at (B.S) University Level Bahawalpur (City)

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ABSTRACT:

These days, due to the advancement of technologies, numerous ways of learning have been introduced including social media platforms, especially social apps, websites and Youtube channels for L2 learning. In this research, the main focus is on social media tools and their effectiveness in second language learning at the university level. The main objectives of this study were to find highly recommended and reliable tools, to find the learners' opinions about social apps, websites, and Youtube channels, and to find the tools of learners' perception about the development of social tools in second language learning. In this research, for the collection of data, a semi-structured questionnaire was utilized, and the population of this research included the students of the 2nd & 3rd semesters of BS level at The Islamia University of Bahawalpur. The data was gathered from Eighty-six students in the English department and tabulated through SPSS version twenty-five. For the analysis of data, percentages, frequencies, mean, standard deviation, Independent sample T-test, and Non- non-parametric test were utilized. The results of the present study reveal that the majority of the students at the BS level utilize these tools for L2 learning, and these tools have a positive impact on students' performance. So, it is concluded that these tools should be utilized for second language learning at the university level, and this research would help the students, teachers, and institutions to understand the significance of social sites, apps, and YouTube channels for L2 learning.

KEYWORDS:

Social Apps, Websites, L2 Learning, University Level, YouTube

Introduction

For learning the English language, the process of utilizing social media was initially designed in Barcelona, Spain, and it proved to be a significant language learning procedure. It was made up of channels, especially for interaction, that allowed the learners of language to boost their four essential skills related to language learning, such as reading, writing, listening, and speaking, and upgrade their transmission (Obar, [2015](#)).

One of the comprehensive electronic techniques that were utilized by the majority of the world's population, almost 3.6 billion consumers of social media, was widely used in 2020 (Abu-Shanab & Al Tarawneh, [2015](#)). Ivanovic, ([2012](#)) argues that amusement and social media that were employed by dissimilar persons on a daily basis could be preferably advantageous for learning English, yet the professional underscore in spite of the fact that Youtube,

Twitter, Facebook, and LinkedIn fascinated numerous consumers and allowed them to intensify their competence of English. These websites were not implied for such motives, so they were not the best choice utilized by learners and motivated those to contemplation the social apps that were constructed for those learners who were interested in acquiring knowledge of the English language. She further explained that general social media platforms could rarely be utilized for education purposes, although they were provided few opportunities for communication and the exchange of ideas.

A confident statement was given by Codrea-Rado (2014) that various tabs and phones gave access to the users to utilize numerous applications and sites that were employed for language learning, such as she suggested Duo lingo application. In this app, programs are constructed to make education more individualized and to point out learner's deficiencies and abilities. These apps are also beneficial for improving grammar and vocabulary and also enhance their communication skills. Thousands of learning apps are utilized by the learners that give them in-depth experiences and suitable virtual environments for second language learning. As a learning platform, YouTube has the capacity to give long-lasting experiences for learners. It is really helpful for distance education learners.

Literature Review

Role of Social Media Tools in L2 Learning

Learning a language effectively has always been considered one of the most important subjects of educational sciences. Lots of theories and assumptions have been put forward, and issues have been criticized. Among all these arguments, motivating the learner and helping them to improve their self-autonomy can be considered the most vital point. In 2020, learners changed their view of the world as well as their way of learning. To be able to catch them, language teachers have numerous options to utilize in our classrooms. At this point, Web 2.0 tools and SNSs (Social et al.) are considered vital. Utilizing our teaching styles in MALL (Mobile Assisted Language Learning) may help us to raise learners' awareness (Baytekin et al., 2021).

Impact of Social Media Tools on the Enhancement of Academic Skills

According to Aforo (2014), the impact of social media suggested that literally social media delivered an effect on the betterment of pupils' English abilities in academic reading. However, he concluded that it didn't have a positive effect on the academic reading skills of learners through the results of his research. The reason was that he figured out that perhaps people on social media could write grammatically inaccurate sentences. For second language learning, the conceptual model should assist the thesis analyses and also the probability of quantifiable vocabulary and grammar fluency through the engagement of social media. Second language learning was regarded up to a point test as compared to learning and understanding the first language because the mother tongue was acquired naturally through atmosphere. A child could learn it through his environment, but learning a second language was not a natural procedure, and the learner could acquire it in class (Allan et al., 2010, p.115).

Positive Part of Social Media in L2 Learning

(Blattner and Fiori, 2011) Described the merit of social media that minimized communication and comprehension. According to (Blattner and Fiori, 2011) human, human beings interchange and share knowledge and material frequently to build new individual and linguistic characteristics on social media. It is an easy way to show their personalities behind screens as a result of obscurity's accelerated surroundings. Al (Ayam Newspaper, 2020) claimed that according to international statistics, social media was massively utilized by Bahrainis with a ratio of 99.7 %. (Al Jahrami, 2019) and Li (2017) both agreed that with the help of social media and online interaction, the learning of L2 learners is enhanced in writing. Gral (2013) stated that social media can be divided into six categories: social news, social networks, bookmarking sites, media sharing, blogging, and micro-blogging. The prominence of these tools had increased in previous years.

The recent study of 8000 faculty members of Babson Survey Research Group stated that faculty members had acquired social media tools and accomplished them efficiently. Social network sites unite mechanical characteristics into one forum, and this interactivity could proceed to the expansion of both relationships and identity. It could display the consequential use of language for particular activities (Reinhardt & Zander, 2011) as well. Blyth, (2008) described that these technological approaches were composed of investigative and illustrative studies. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the prospective advantage of the specific tool. There was a lack of theoretical framework in this study. He gave the introduction of new technologies and their contribution to L2 learning, especially for second language learners.

Social Media as a Source of Language Development

Social media was overfilled with interconnection, and interconnections were a little bit of a contributor to the procedure of learning a language. In the process of language learning, the researchers highlighted the concern of social media, which was in the form of an electronic gadget that was the newest in the procedure of second language learning. Social media has played an essential role in promoting language learning and distributing a wide range of genuine data (Ansari & Khan, 2020). Gibreel (2018) highlighted that for English language learning and the advantages of the utilization of social media, a large number of suppositions could be faced when investigating the opinions of English language learners. The people should be associated with numerous customs and nations, particularly with the native speakers who have adapted the English language to a broader level. The large scale of the usage of the English language on social media platforms and a considerable number of disclosures were to enhance the passion among English language learners.

Role of Social Apps in L2 Learning

According to the most recent information available on Statista (2020), there are round about 3.96 billion social media customers across the board. Microblogs such as Twitter, internet sites and Apps as Snapchat, LinkedIn Facebook, YouTube, Instagram and LinkedIn are samples of online networking sites. However, individuals' social, educational, and personal lives have been impacted by these various platforms or social media Apps.

Impact of Social Applications on Second Language Learning

Al-Jarrah and Talafhah, (2019).) Pointed out that it is an accessible and easy way for university-going students to learn through social apps in contrast to traditional methods such as books and text content available in the library. With the help of social media, not only students' writing abilities are improved, but also, with the availability of pictures and videos, their skills are improved. According to (StatistaInc, 2015), due to the development of Mobile technologies, a huge amount of language learning programs are developed. There are almost millions of applications that are accessible to consumers not only in the Play Store but also in the Apple iTunes app store, and educational apps account for 9.95% of them.

Role of EFD Applications in L2 Learning

Çelik and Yavuz (2018) claimed that mobile applications assisted in amalgamating mobile phones into drastically exchanging education that was instantly personalized, omnipresent, student-centered, and unstrained. The productivity of mobile phone applications, in which the main focus was on vocabulary directions in both literal and contextual ways. They claimed that mobile applications were successful in language learning, and they also notified that their applications must be accomplished in a directed and organized way, while a few applications were not developed by specialists. Zhang (2016) conducted research on the application English Fun Dubbing (EFD) to check its effectiveness, and he declared that this app assisted the pupils in learning sovereignty by giving them a chance to exercise without haste. He further explained that a suitable option for a worthy application intensified learning and made it easier for the learners to use smart devices in a more appropriate way than they generally used.

Assessment of Mobile Applications in Second Language Acquisition

(Reinders and White, [2011](#)) Pointed out that to hold up second language learning, mobile techniques had the capability to give independent chances and approaches for the learning content. Research gave little proof that numerous applications could assist intermediate learners of English language students by providing them with unaccomplished approaches to English material that regulate their concerns. These applications could give constant chances for genuine second language communication that could be complicated to get along linguistically and culturally analogous countries such as Japan (Aubrey & Nowlan, [2013](#), p.129). Reinders and Program ([2016](#)) explained the substructure for the assessment of mobile applications and also recorded the significance of debating the results of second language acquisition and teacher education while assessing applications. Second language acquisition had basic demands for extensive information, consultation of meaning in interconnection, and observing of novel language; the final could be encouraged by the productive response.

Usage of Applications as Instructional Tools of Second Language Learning

Srivastava ([2012](#)) sustained those online forums where the focal point was to make possible the construction of connections among people with allocated profits, backdrops, and reality-based interrelations that supply golden chances for browser-based interrelation. The application of social media means was utilized as an instructional tool to influence second language acquisition. According to Chawinga ([2017](#)), it was acclaimed that due to the shortage of face-to-face connection among learners, they were utilizing Twitter eventually to enhance learners' involvement. Compared to classroom situations where open-ended questions were asked of the pupils, they remained entirely muted. When the same question was inquired over, Twitter would obtain a noteworthy feedback rate.

Role of Social Sites in L2 learning

(Echeburúa, [2013](#)) argues that an online website where a user can create a profile and build a personal network that connects them to other users is known as a social networking site. The worldwide phenomenon of social networking has spread very quickly.

Role of social networking sites in L2 learning

The research was conducted on a group of Malaysian university students, and a large number of participants confirmed that social sites had helpful impressions on their educational production. (Gomez et al., [2012](#)) claimed that social networking sites were helpful for pupils in solving educational inquiries relevant to the material of their exams or courses and that they could get knowledge while they were absent from class. These sites were really beneficial for them in accomplishing tasks. In social networking sites where in the process of second language learning, learners were motivated in an efficacious atmosphere, and through it, their skills were also developed and polished (Nielsen, [2024](#)).

Social Sites Provide Numerous Chances of Learning

Meier ([2013](#)) emphasized that numerous social networking sites, including chat-based sites, blogs, emails, and messengers, should be well aware of educational existence in the context of a second language. His research concluded that these online communication forums took part in assisting learners' assimilation and were also associated with their own culture and language. Whenever pupils endeavored to immerse themselves in a fresh educational setting, these researchers delivered relevant confirmation of the effectual method of operating social network sites. (McLoughlin & Lee [2008](#)) preserved that the social site of educational instruments was for the disclosure, distribution, construction of information, material formation, and instinctive chances of learning. Additionally, social networking sites have been ascribed to the capability to assist cooperative learning, involving persons in analytical thinking and intensifying transmission and writing abilities with the help of the effort of energetic members in a customized atmosphere (Ajjan et al., [2008](#)).

Role of Online Exercises Available at Social Sites

(Brick, [2011](#)) elevated three major questions: Should social networking sites be merged into the syllabus? Do learners require instruction to operate them? Should online exercises be accommodated entirely for higher education and correlated with the online electronic learning atmosphere? Should pupils of foreign/second language navigate on their own in this exceedingly expanding cybernetics space without getting any proper training from their tutors? Due to the enhancement of electronic learning forums and the development of social media channels, these questions await accurate solutions. (Clark & Gruba, [2010](#)), Zourou ([2012](#)) and (Liu et al., [2013](#)) stated that the learners had an insufficiency of comprehension of how social networking sites could be accustomed to expedite the learning and teaching for tutors and pupils of English as a second language.

Development of Discrete Capacities by Utilizing Social Sites

Nokelainen ([2006](#)) diagnosed ten pedagogical accessibilities of benchmark pupils' control, activities, collective, associative learning, ambition, appropriateness, contribution, inspiration appraisal, appreciation of background knowledge, mold abilities, assessment, and established their significance in his experiential study by analyzing elementary school learners through the survey. Testing tools could also be helpful in providing precious details concerning how students make use of and outlook social networking sites for second language learners. Language students were gratified by the distinctive occasions delivered through the help of virtual interaction platforms of language learning to exercise their spoken expertise with mother-tongue speakers and to collect approximately instant evaluations. In spite of that, they also found fault with the accessible academic content. Furthermore, researchers noted that trainers integrate flow systems,, for instance. Social networking sites in their language classrooms are required to be the conscious opportunity of unsuitable progress and digital filtering from other site users. In these socially networked gaps, learners with distinct attentiveness were motivated to develop their discrete capacities and to devote apprehension where each person within the group could take advantage (Gee, [2004](#), p.79).

Utilization of Social Networking Sites for Numerous Purposes

Krug ([2005](#)), in his volume, Don't "Make Me Think," asserts the significance of manufacturing the pattern of a website perceptive, comprehensible, and accessible. Operators should be capable of detecting methods to operate a website without observing a workshop. Understandable and accurate tags and word options for the sites of language learning developed are even more salient. The reason behind this was that the site exploration might not be for L1 learners. Brake, ([2009](#)) marked that Social networking sites were employed for numerous aims, such as for distributing details, acculturation, and interchange. The internet apps, tools, and domains had been arranged into progressively wide viewpoints regarding the resemblance, joint endeavor, and revealing for the social groundwork operation, video, audio, print, live recording, photo exchanging, microblogging, creativity applications, inspection, gaming, rich side review, interactive and mobile. (Fraser, [2000](#)) declared that the chance of social connection was the attitude that described the discipline of language learning in full scale of informal co-relational areas. From the point of view of social interaction, the task of intervention was censorious in the development of learners' learning.

Role of Youtube Channels in L2 learning

There has been a lot of research on how to utilize Youtube clips to master English as a second language learner. (Chien et al., [2020](#)) found that using YouTube in the English classroom accommodated EFL College students to retain and understand what they were listening to. Additionally, Syafiq et al. ([2021](#)) found that using YouTube videos as English learning materials improved students' speaking skills, including fluency, vocabulary, pronunciation, grammar, and content. Even so, (Sari et al., [2020](#)) claimed that the video project gave EFL students a chance to grow creatively. Concerning discoveries, the analyst feels intrigued to concentrate more on the use of YouTube recordings in the education of English, especially in showing listening abilities. The purpose of this study was to find out if students' listening comprehension performance was significantly improved by watching videos on YouTube.

Usage of YouTube Channels to Instruct English as a Second Language

McDonough and Shaw (2003) pointed out that prognosis helped pupils to generate hints that gave them the opportunity to acknowledge the explanation of educational chores. At the start of the YouTube video, it was essential to read out the title and purpose of the video. Watching the pictures relevant to the material would also assist the pupils in acquiring earlier knowledge. (Erben et al., 2009) argued that English language learners not only looked at kinesics but also focused on verbal expressions in the videos on YouTube and garbled the meanings of lines. Tarantino (2011) claimed that several researchers noticed that there was a deficiency of inquisition about the impact of YouTube videos on second language learning (English). A small-scale empirical examination was conducted to explain effectual methods for integrating browser-based applications into foreign language directions. Teachers of Language might not have a sufficient milieu or understanding of the effective influence of YouTube videos on teaching objectives. YouTube is regarded as an appealing social media platform that is devoted to worldwide education, and YouTube is increasingly utilized by tutors to teach the English language (Bonk, 2009).

Utilization of YouTube videos in the Classroom for L2 Learning

Alexa (2014) pointed out that the majority of language instructors use these websites and YouTube videos to instruct English, and YouTube has been converted into the most famous website in the whole world. By viewing accurate videos in the classroom, the process of learning can develop. Furthermore, researchers have frequently predicted that YouTube is an efficacious instrument that can construct students' comprehension and assist them in upgrading their fluidity of English. YouTube videos can assist pupils in interacting and encountering the occurrences in the videos. Valid YouTube videos can enhance pupils' understanding and extract details. It gives them a chance to recognize the session in a successful and energetic way. These channels represent the session more rationally and more extensively than the classical method of teaching (Sherman, 2003).

(Montero et al., 2017) The research focused on the consequence of the disclosure of YouTube videos in second language vocabulary procreation. By watching videos, they learned vocabulary and described the vocabulary capacity of participators immediately associated with the reasoning skills that were advanced by utilizing the situation in the videos they disclosed. (Kelsen's, 2009) announced that additional videos taken from YouTube were considered to be fascinating, pertinent, and useful. He further explained that YouTube content slightly motivated the learner in the class as compared to outdoors.

Availability of YouTube Videos Related to Language Learning

A forecast given by McDonough and Shaw (2003) was really beneficial for the learners in generating hints that allowed them to recognize the connotation of an educational piece of work. Furthermore, at the start, pay attention to the name given in the YouTube video, understand the goals of the tutorial video, and look at pictures that were associated with the material in the video. Then, concentrate on the description given in the YouTube video. It would assist the learners in operating on their previous comprehension. According to (Faizi, 2018), with the arrival of YouTube, videos related to language learning were easily obtainable. These days, both tutors and students of English have requested videos but are not completely reliant on the outmoded class of language learning. The reason behind this is that You Tube

learners acquire a huge range of videos relevant to English language learning and teaching.

Role of YouTube Videos in the Advancement of English Knowledge

As Mayer (2001) explained, a multivariate method provided approachable videos in the whole region of knowledge. The application of YouTube could be regarded as a beneficial means of learning as additional research has expressed important results in using the combination of video clips in tutoring. Mayer had already declared that video was exceptionally effective for inaugural courses. The reason behind this was that it could enable the way to understand

complicated ideas and gain learners' concentration. (Nofrika, 2019) concluded that on YouTube channels, numerous types of videos were watched by learners of the English language, and through it, they could easily advance their knowledge of English. He further explained that three types of YouTube videos were frequently viewed by learners: vlogs, social science, and art and humanities.

Research Methodology

Research Questions

- Q 1: Which kind of role do social apps, websites, and YouTube channels play in acquiring English as a second language?
- Q 2: What is the learners' point of view about the tools, especially social apps, websites, and Youtube channels, in L2 learning?
- Q 3: How do the learners perceive the development of social tools and their major role in L2 learning?

Questionnaire

The researcher has utilized self – a structured questionnaire for the collection of data because the study is descriptive in nature. This type of research utilizes the questions as an instrument for the collection of data. Rensis (1932) argues that to compute the behaviors, the emblematic Likert scale 5 or 7-point ordinal scale was utilized by the participants to give the rank of the given statement to which they agreed or disagreed. In the current research, the researcher has utilized a five 5-point Likert scale that is constructed of 5 points ranging from one point to another with a neutral point in it. In the questionnaire, the researcher also includes demographic information such as Name, Age, and Gender. The major role of gathering background information of the participants is to identify the effect of numerous demographic factors on second language learning students at the Bs level. The questionnaire comprises 30 Likert-formatted questions that examine the development of the tools, including social apps, social sites, and YouTube channels in second language learning. The questionnaire is divided into three sections, and in each section, 10 questions are included. The 1st section consists of questions regarding social apps, the 2nd section comprises questions regarding social sites, and the 3rd section contains questions regarding YouTube channels.

Population of the Study

The target population is defined as the whole population from which the researcher wants to conduct research. A sampling frame was drawn from this target population. Therefore, in this study, the target population is all the pupils of BS level 2nd and 3rd semester in the English department of Islamia University Bahawalpur. The accessible population means the part of the target population known as the study population. Actually, the researcher draws their sample from the accessible population.

Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using SPSS software. Using descriptive statistics, the researcher measured the percentages, frequencies, and mean scores. The researcher used T-tests and non-parametric tests to determine the differences of opinions between genders.

T-tests and non-parametric tests were utilized by the researcher to determine the genders' opinions.

Demographic Information

Table 1

Frequency and percentage of respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	39	45.3%
Female	47	54.7%
Total	86	100%

Table 1 shows that there were 86 participants who participated in the study. Out of these 86 participants, there were 39 (45.3%) males, and 47 (54.7%) females. The sample for data collection comprised BS 2nd semester and BS 3rd semester at the English department in The Islamia University of Bahawalpur. The data analysis shows that the majority of the respondents were male.

Table 2

Age of participants (Frequency and percentage of age of respondents)

Years	Frequency	Percent
18 to 21	63	73.3%
22 to 25	23	26.7%
Total	86	100%

Table no 2 indicates the age of 86 participants who were taken as a sample from the English department of The Islamia University of Bahawalpur at the BS level. After the data analysis, it was concluded that out of 86 participants, 63 (73.3%) were between 18 to 21 years while 23 (26.7%) were between 22 to 25 years. The majority of the participants were between 18 and 21 years old, while the minimum was between 22 and 25 years old.

Percentages of Social Apps

Table 1

Percentages of Social Apps

Students' Reviews About Social Apps;	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1. L2 learners are motivated and stimulated through social apps.	26.7%	67.4%	4.7%	0%	1.2%
2. Social apps encourage L2 learners to understand a second language easily.	29.1%	60.5%	9.3%	1.2%	0%
3. Four basic skills of L2 learners are being developed through social apps.	20.9%	47.7%	24.4%	5.8%	1.2%
4. Drills and exercises on social apps are beneficial to enhance second language learning	18.6%	60.5%	15.1%	5.8%	1.2%
5. Applications of ELSA and CAKE are significant for second language learning.	10.5%	51.2%	32.6%	4.7%	1.2%
6. Pictures and videos on social apps help out to develop second language knowledge.	37.2%	53.5%	7.0%	1.2%	1.2%
7. Social apps are helpful to improve learners' vocabulary and communication skills.	45.3%	52.3%	1.2%	1.2%	0%
8. Social apps are the best way to test learners' skills in the real world.	20.9%	50.0%	18.6%	10.5%	0%
9. Social apps are valuable for practicing a new language.	24.4%	59.3%	12.8%	3.5%	0%
10. Social apps develop learners' interest in learning a second language.	31.4%	50.0%	11.6%	4.7%	2.3%

Percentages of Social Sites

Table 2

Percentages of social sites

Students Review About Social Sites;	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
11. Learners utilize social sites for the development of their second language learning.	15.1%	60.5%	22.1%	2.3%	0%
12. Learners' skills improve due to the availability of social sites.	30.2%	54.7%	8.1%	5.8%	1.2%
13. To increase awareness of a second language, the use of social sites is enhanced day by day.	40.7%	46.5%	8.1%	3.5%	1.2%
14. The development occurs in second language learning through exercises available at sites.	20.9%	52.3%	23.3%	1.2%	2.3%
15. L2 learners motivate, encourage, and develop their interest in learning through sites.	33.7%	48.8%	12.8%	3.5%	1.2%
16. Social sites are helpful in minimizing mistakes and grammatical errors in a second language.	17.4%	45.3%	26.7%	10.5%	0%
17. Social sites assist learners in connecting with language learning and educational groups.	23.3%	60.5%	14.0%	1.2%	1.2%
18. Social networks provide multiple opportunities for learners and institutions to improve learning methods	32.6%	57.0%	8.1%	1.2%	1.2%
19. Social sites help L2 learners accelerate their learning by being up-to-date and self-directed.	23.3%	55.8%	14.0%	5.8%	1.2%
20. Social sites are a fast way to learn a second language.	32.6%	45.3%	15.1%	5.8%	1.2%

Percentages of Youtube Channels

Table 3

Percentages of YouTube channels

Students Review About Youtube Channels;	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
21. Second language learners utilize YouTube videos for better understanding.	45.3%	46.5%	5.8%	2.3%	0%
22. Videos of native speakers help non-Native learners improve their accents.	27.9%	58.1%	12.8%	1.2%	0%
23. The Reading, listening, writing, and speaking skills of L2 learners are polished through YouTube videos.	27.9%	52.3%	14%	5.8%	0%

Students Review About Youtube Channels;	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
24. The Vocabulary and pronunciation of L2 learners are gradually enhanced through YouTube videos.	25.6%	58.1%	12.8%	3.5%	0%
25. For second language learning, the usage of Youtube channels is enhanced day by day.	43%	50%	5.8%	1.2%	0%
26. YouTube channels are a good platform for second language learning.	40.7%	41.9%	11.6%	3.5%	2.3%
27. YouTube channels are helpful in enhancing learners' fluency in a second language.	23.3%	61.6%	15.1%	0%	0%
28. Online YouTube courses enhance learners' proficiency in communicating in a second language.	23.3%	59.3%	16.3%	1.2%	0%
29. YouTube is a great entertainment tool for second language learning.	38.4%	45.3%	12.8%	3.5%	0%
30. YouTube is a visual learning tool to enhance the capability of second language learners.	31.4%	54.7%	14%	0%	0%

Result of Genders' Opinion about Social Apps

Levine's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means	
F	Sig.	t	Df
.713	.401	.538	84
		.543	83.361

The results indicate that there is no significant difference in the opinion of males and females, $t(84) = .538, p = .401$. The mean score of the male ($M = 4.0538, SD = .35007$) is not significantly different from the female ($M = 4.0106, SD = .38743$) score. Cohen's $d = .11$ represented that there is no significant difference between the opinions of the two genders.

Result of Genders' Opinions about Social Sites

		Levine's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means	
		F	Sig.	T	df
Social Sites	Equal variances assumed	1.731	.192	2.685	84
	Equal variances are not assumed.			2.732	84.000

An independent T-test was conducted to examine gender differences among the students of BS. Levene's test for equality of variance shows no violation, $p = .192$. Results indicate that males ($M = 4.1256, SD = .34083$) mean score is greater than females ($M = 3.9043, SD = .41070$) means score states $t(84) = 2.685, p > 0.05$. Cohen's $d = .586$ shows the difference between the opinions of the two genders.

Result of Genders' Opinion about Youtube Channels

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means	
		F	Sig.	T	Df
YouTube	Equal variances assumed	.010	.922	3.561	84
	Equal variances are not assumed.			3.590	83.143

An independent T-test was conducted to examine gender differences among the students of BS. Levene's test for equality of variance shows no violation, $p = .922$. Results indicate that the males' ($M = 4.3128, SD = .35702$) mean score is greater than the females' ($M = 4.0234, SD = .38966$) mean score states $t(84) = 3.56, p > 0.05$. Cohen's $d = 0.77$ shows the difference between the opinions of two genders. Cohen's d .

Results of the Non-Parametric Test

The result of the nonparametric test indicates that in the first variable, the mean rank of female participants is 42.86, and the mean rank of male participants is 44.27. There is no significant difference between the opinion of both genders and the mean score is .794, greater than 0.05. In the second variable, the mean rank of female participants is 37.78, and the mean rank of male participants is 50.40. There is a difference between the opinion of both genders and the mean score is 0.19, less than the significance level of 0.05. In the third variable, the mean rank of female participants is 35.68, and the mean rank of male participants is 52.92. There is a difference between the opinion of both genders and the mean score is .001, less than 0.05.

Hypothesis Test Summary

S. No	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The distribution of social is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	0.794	Retain the null hypothesis.
2	The distribution of Socialists is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	0.019	Reject the null hypothesis.
3	The distribution of YouTube is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	0.001	Reject the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic Significance is displayed, and the significance level is 25.

Findings

Development of Social Apps

The second part of this research is about the development of Social apps for L2 learning. The results are gathered from

BS (second & third) level students through a self-designed 5-point Likert scale questionnaire (Strongly, Agree, Neutral, disagree and strongly disagree).

The result of 1st statement shows that the majority of the participants, 67.4%, agree, 26.7% strongly agree, 4.7% are neutral, and 1.2% strongly disagree about the motivation and stimulation of L2 learners through social apps. The result tabulated from the 2nd statement expresses that a large amounts of participants, 60.5%, agree, 29.1% strongly agree, 9.3%, neutral, and 1.2% disagree about the understanding of a second language easily through social apps. The result gathered from 3rd statement shows that almost 44.7% of participants agree, 24.4% neutral, 20.9% strongly agree, 5.8% disagree, and 1.2% strongly agree about the development of 4 basic skills of L2 learners through social apps. The result of the 4th statement expresses that a large amounts of participants, almost 60.5% agree, 18.6% strongly agree, 15.1 % are neutral, 5.8% disagree, 1.2% strongly disagree about the enhancement of drills, and

exercises on social apps are beneficial for second language learning.

The result of the 5th statement shows that almost 51.2% of participants agree, 32.6 neutral, 10.5% strongly agree, 4.7% disagree & 1.2% strongly disagree about the significance role of the applications of CAKE and ELSA for second language learning. The result of the 6th statement expresses that almost 53.5% of participants agree, 37.2% strongly agree, 7.0% neutral, 1.2% disagree, and 1.2% strongly disagree about the development of second language knowledge with the help of pictures and videos at social apps. The result of the 7th statement shows that almost

52.3% of participants agree, 45.3% strongly agree, 1.2% neutral, and 1.2% disagree about the improvement of learners' vocabulary and communication skills through social apps.

The result of the 8th statement expresses that almost 50.0% agree, 20.9% strongly agree, 18.6% are neutral, and 10.5% disagree with the statement that the best way to test learners' skills in the real world is through social apps. The result of the 9th statement expresses that the majority of the participants, almost 59.3%, agree, 24.4% strongly agree, 12.8% neutral, and 3.5% disagree that the practicing of new language social apps are valuable. The result of the 10th statement shows that almost 50.3% agree, 31.4% strongly agree, 11.6% are neutral, and 4.7% disagree, while 2.3% strongly disagree about the development of learners' interest in learning a second language through social apps.

The result of the T-test indicates that there is no significant difference in the opinion of males and females, $t(84) = .538$, $p = .401$, and first part consists of 10 statements. The mean score of male participants ($M = 4.0538$, $SD = .35007$) is not significantly different from the mean score ($M = 4.0106$, $SD = .38743$) of female participants. Cohen's $d = .11$ represents that there is no significant difference between the opinions of both genders. The result of independent samples Mann-Whitney U Test showed the p-value is .794, and the decision is to retain the null hypothesis.

Development of Social Sites

Third part of this study is about the development of Social networking websites for L2 learning. The results are gathered from BS (second & third) level students through a self-designed 5-point Likert scale questionnaire (Strongly, Agree, Neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree).

The result of 11th statement indicates that majority of pupils almost 60.5% agree, 22.1% neutral, 15.1% strongly agree & 2.3% disagree about the application of social websites in support of the development in second language learning. The result of statement number twelve expresses that almost 54.7% of participants agree, 30.2% strongly agree, 8.1% neutral, and 5.8% disagree, while 1.2% strongly disagree about the improvement of learners' skills due to the availability of social sites. The result of the 13th statement shows that 46.5% agree, 40.7% strongly agree, 8.1% neutral, and 3.5% disagree & 1.2% strongly disagree about the utilization of social sites that are enhanced day by day due to the awareness of a second language.

The result of the 14th statement indicates that almost 52.3% of participants agree, 23.3% neutral, 20.9% strongly agree, 2.3% strongly disagree, and 1.2% disagree about the development of second language learning through exercises available at social sites. The result of the 15th statement expresses that almost 48.8% agree, 33.7% strongly agree, 12.8% neutral, 3.5% disagree, and 1.2% strongly disagree about the motivation, encouragement, and development of Second language pupils' engrossment in academic attainment through social sites.

The result of statement number sixteen shows that almost 45.3% agree, 26.7% are neutral, 17.4% strongly agree, and 10.5% disagree about the minimization of mistakes and grammatical errors in a second language through social sites. The result of the 17th statement indicates that a large amount of participants, almost 60.5%, agree, 23.3% strongly agree, 14.0% are neutral, 1.2% disagree & 1.2% strongly disagree about the learners' connection with language learning and educational groups through social sites. The result of the 18th statement shows that almost 57.0% agree, 32.6% strongly agree, 8.1% are neutral, 1.2% disagree, and 1.2% strongly disagree about the multiple opportunities for learners and instructors to improve learning methods provided by social sites.

The result of the 19th statement shows that almost 55.8% agree, 23.3% strongly agree, 14.0% are neutral, 5.8% disagree, and 1.2% strongly disagree about the acceleration of L2 learners by being up-to-date and self-directed through social sites. The result of the 20th statement expresses that 45.3% agree, 32.6% strongly agree, 15.1% are neutral, and 5.8% disagree, 1.2% strongly disagree that social site is the fastest way to learn a second language.

An independent sample T-Test was conducted to examine the gender difference in social sites among the students of BS Level 2nd & 3rd semester. Levene's test for equality of variance shows no violation, $p = .192$. Results indicate that males' ($M = 4.1256$, $SD = .34083$) mean score is greater than females' ($M = 3.9043$, $SD = .41070$) mean score states $t(84) = 2.685$, $p > 0.05$ and Cohen's $d = .586$ shows the difference between the opinions of two genders. The result of independent samples Mann-Whitney U Test shows the p -value is $.019$, and the decision is to reject the null hypothesis.

Development of Youtube Channels

Fourth part of this research is about the development of Youtube channels for L2 learning. The results are gathered from BS (second & third) level students through a self-designed 5-point Likert scale questionnaire (Strongly, Agree, Neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree).

The result of the 21st statement shows that almost 45.67% of participants agree, 45.3% strongly agree, 5.8% are neutral, and 2.3% disagree about the utilization of YouTube videos for a better understanding of second language learners. The result of the 22nd statement expresses that almost 58.1% of participants agree, 27.9% strongly agree, 12.8% neutral & 1.2% disagree about the improvement of the accent of non-native speakers through the videos of native speakers. The result of the 23rd statement indicates that almost 52.3% of participants agree, 27.9% strongly agree, 14% are neutral, and 5.8% disagree about the listening, reading, writing, and speaking skills of L2 learners that are polished through YouTube videos. The result of the 24th statement expresses that almost 58.1% agree, 25.6% strongly agree, 12.8% are neutral, and 3.5% disagree about the enhancement of vocabulary and pronunciation of L2 learners through YouTube videos.

The result of the 25th statement shows that almost 50% of participants agree, 43% strongly agree, 5.8% neutral & 1.2% disagree about the enhancement of second language learning through the usage of Youtube channels day by day. The result of the 26th statement indicates that almost 41.9% agree, 40.7% strongly agree, 11.6% are neutral, 3.5% disagree, and 2.3% strongly disagree about the good platform for second language learning is the YouTube channel. The result of the 27th statement shows that a large number of participants, almost 61.6%, agree, 23.3% strongly agree, and 15.1% are neutral about the enhancement of learners' fluency in a second language through YouTube channels.

The result of the 28th statement expresses that 59.3% agree, 23.3% strongly agree, 16.3% are neutral, and 1.2% disagree about the enhancement of learners' proficiency to communicate in a second language through online YouTube courses. The result of the 29th statement shows that almost 45.3% agree, 38.4% strongly agree, 12.8% are neutral, and 3.5% disagree that the great entertainment tool of second language learning is YouTube. The result of the 30th statement expresses that 54.7% agree, 31.4% strongly disagree, and 14% are neutral about the enhancement of the capacity of second language learners; YouTube is a visual learning tool.

The result of an independent sample T-test is conducted to examine the gender difference among the students of BS level in the 2nd and 3rd semesters. Levene's test for equality of variance shows no violation, $p = .922$. Results indicate that males' ($M = 4.3128$, $SD = .35702$) mean score is greater than females' ($M = 4.0234$, $SD = .38966$) mean score states $t(84) = 3.56$, $p > 0.05$ Cohen's $d = 0.77$ shows a difference between the opinions of two genders. The result of independent samples Mann-Whitney U Test shows the p -value is $.001$, and the decision is to reject the null hypothesis.

Conclusions

In light of the above-mentioned results, it is concluded that social apps, sites, and YouTube channels are developing and playing a significant role in L2 learning at the (BS) university level. The current study is guided by the given conclusions. In light of the results of the current study, it is concluded that the pupils of BS (2nd & 3rd semester) at

the university level have positive perceptions regarding the development of social apps, sites, and youtube channels for second language acquisition.

The present study reveals that social tools, including apps, sites, and YouTube channels, play a significant role in motivating and stimulating L2 learners. The results of the given study reveal that not only are the four basic skills of the learners developed, but their vocabulary and communication skills are also improved through these social tools. With the help of the pictures and videos available on social media sites, including channels, apps, learners' vocabulary, pronunciation, and the four basic skills of reading, writing, listening, and speaking are polished.

Mistakes and errors are improved by the utilization of these social tools, and learners learn things easily with the help of practice and drills available on social sites, apps, and YouTube channels. These tools are considered a good platform and a fast way of learning because learners' interest is enhanced through it. Due to the availability of videos of native speakers, the accent of non-native speakers has improved. Second-language learners accelerate their learning by being updated through these social tools.

For the improvement of the learning methods, multiple opportunities are provided for the learners, and with the help of social tools, pupils are connected easily with one another. For a second language, especially for new language learning, social tools are the best way to test learners' skills in the real world. No doubt that these tools are a great source of entertainment, but they are also playing a vital role in enhancing learners' proficiency in communicating in second language acquisition.

Suggestions and Recommendations

After getting the results of the present study, several recommendations are given below:

The results of the present study reveal that social apps, sites, and YouTube channels are developing and playing a significant role in L2 learning at the (BS) university level; therefore, it is also recommended that all university-level learners use these social tools for second language learning. The present study expresses that social tools, including apps, sites, and YouTube channels, play a significant role in motivating and stimulating L2 learners, so it is recommended for the pupils of 2nd language learners to utilize these tools.

The results of the given study shows that not only four basic skills, but also vocabulary and communication skills are improved through these social tools; therefore it is recommended for the students of university level to utilize it for the enhancement of all skills. It is recommended that universities utilize these social tools for second language learning because learners learn quickly with the help of pictures and videos available in it. Keeping in view that mistakes and errors are improved through these social tools, it is recommended that university students, especially English language learners, utilize these sources for L2 learning.

It is revealed that due to the availability of videos for native speakers, the accent of non-native speakers has improved. Second language learners accelerate their learning by being updated through these social tools; therefore, it is recommended that universities should utilize these tools for the improvement of accents. These tools are recommended for better communication and connection with one another. The communication skills of university-level students are enhanced through it.

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